

“Modelling tree internal decay and cavity development to reduce uncertainties in large tree carbon estimates”

Cristina Alejandra Serrano (Student no. 730691)

Master of Forest Ecosystem Science

October 2016

School of Ecosystem and Forest Sciences | Faculty of Science

The University of Melbourne

Supervisor: Dr. Cristina Aponte

Abstract

Enhancing our capacity to estimate carbon stocks in large trees has become increasingly important in the context of climate change. Large living trees are likely to develop internal decomposition resulting in internal cavities. As the wood decomposes within large trees, the strength and structure of the wood is lost overtime. The loss of internal biomass may be significant, having a potential impact on the total carbon stocks. A study conducted in the cool temperate forests of southeastern Australia assessed the internal decomposition using a resistograph and CODIT model in 21 *Eucalyptus regnans* and 22 *Nothofagus cunninghamii* to reduce uncertainties in carbon estimates. Adjusted biomass calculations that discount internal decomposition was estimated for the stand of four sites of wet forests and rainforests in the southeast of the Central Highland of Victoria. The findings of this research suggest that there is a strong relationship between internal cavities and diameter. However, early and advanced internal decay is more variable across the diameter distribution. Logistic regressions demonstrated that *N. cunninghamii* has a high probability of developing internal cavities as diameter increases. However, internal decomposition is highly variable across diameter distribution particularly in *E. regnans*, which limited statistical predictive models. Our findings show that adjusted biomass slightly decreases in total biomass compared to other studies, particularly when trees are greater than 100cm dbh. Assessing the internal decay/cavity is crucial to reduce uncertainties and improve estimates of carbon stocks in the cool temperate forests.

Keywords: *Carbon, internal decomposition, temperate forest.*

Declaration

I declare this thesis has been composed by my own work. Scientific literature has been properly acknowledged and referenced throughout the entire thesis.

This thesis is 9,192 words excluding tables, maps, references and appendices.

Cristina Alejandra Serrano

31st October 2016.

Acknowledgments

First, I would like to express my gratitude to Dr. Lauren Bennett and my supervisor Dr. Cristina Aponte for this Master research opportunity. I want to extend my gratitude to my supervisor for her patience, enthusiastic and consistent support, advice and comments during the fieldwork and over the process of this thesis. Furthermore, I would like to acknowledge Dr. Denise Johnstone and PhD student Luis Orozco for their support and advice in the expertise of wood decay. Also, I would like to thank the help of technicians Julio Najera and Ben Smith in collecting data and sharing their knowledge about the southeastern cool temperate forests of the Central Highlands of Victoria, Australia. Lastly, I would like to thank my loved ones for their unconditional support over the entire process of this thesis and the culmination of my master degree.

Content

Abstract	1
Declaration	2
Acknowledgments.....	3
1. Introduction	6
1.1. The process of internal decay/cavity	8
1.2. Decay/cavity impact on biomass estimates	9
1.3. Horizontal and vertical spread of decay	10
1.4. Decay/cavity and diameter	11
2. Methods	13
2.1. Fieldwork measurements.....	13
2.2. Decay/cavity estimates	14
2.3. Decay/cavity volume and biomass.....	15
3. Results	17
3.1. Probability of decay/cavity.....	18
3.2. The volume of internal decomposition.....	19
3.3. Impact on carbon stocks	20
4. Discussion.....	23
4.1. Internal decomposition and diameter	23
4.2. Internal decomposition and environmental conditions	23
4.3. Internal decomposition volume based on diameter.....	23
4.4. Decomposing biomass and carbon stocks	24
4.5. Further research.....	26
5. Conclusions	26
References.....	28
Appendices.....	31
Appendix a.....	31
Appendix b.....	32
Appendix c.....	33
Appendix d.....	34
Appendix e.....	35

Appendix f.	36
Appendix g.....	37
Appendix h.....	38

List of figures

Figure 1	8
Figure 2	8
Figure 3	9
Figure 4	11
Figure 5	11
Figure 6	12
Figure 7	13
Figure 8	15
Figure 9	15
Figure 10	17
Figure 11	17
Figure 12	18
Figure 13	18
Figure 14	19
Figure 15	19
Figure 16	20
Figure 17	20
Figure 18	21
Figure 19	21
Figure 20	24
Figure 21	24

List of tables

Table 1	22
Table 2	25

1. Introduction

The assessment of forests for potential carbon storage is a well-established concept in forestry that has gained significant attention in studies on global climate change (Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2015). The levels of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere have been increasing globally in the last few decades (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005). The principal causes of increasing CO₂ are the combustion of fossil fuels and land-use changes (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005). The main causes are associated with the greenhouse effects, in which temperatures rise due to its dependence on the CO₂ levels in the atmosphere (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005). Governments around the world have committed to climate change initiatives by participating in the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Therefore, assessing the contribution of CO₂ and evaluating the process to control CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere have become imperative. In this context, the ecosystem services of terrestrial ecosystems have also gained important attention. The concept of ecosystem services was first developed by the Millennium Assessment (2005) and embodies the idea that forest ecosystems can provide multi-dimensional benefits (Amacher, Ollikainen & Uusivuori 2014). Trees can contribute to climate change by sequestering carbon in their biomass, however, they can also provide socio-economic and environmental benefits at the same time (Canadell & Raupach 2008). Among these benefits, carbon storage is defined as a non-wood value which provides resilience towards climate change (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005).

Carbon assessment focuses on measuring living and dead organic matter that contains and releases carbon (Zheng et al. 2015). Decomposition is an important component in carbon studies and it has mainly focused on leaves, small branches, fruits (known as fallen litter) and standing dead trunks, logs and snags (known as coarse woody debris) (Zheng et al. 2015). However, decomposition in living trees that result in the loss of wood has been studied less (Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Zheng et al. 2015). Large trees in old-growth forests are likely to develop internal decay and cavities which are a result of slowly decomposing internal wood in their biomass (Zheng et al. 2015). Large trees in old-growth forests can store large amount of carbon due to their size (Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2015). However, little is known about how significant the impact of internal decomposition is on the total biomass of large trees (Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Zheng et al. 2015). Although old-growth trees occupy a small fraction of the total area of a forest, they can hold at least 40% of the total biomass (Zheng et al. 2015). Evidence suggests that the development of internal decomposition may result in overestimating biomass in large trees, which may have a significant impact on the total forest carbon stock estimates (Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2015). These uncertainties need to be addressed to enhance calculations, monitoring decay and finally, report carbon stocks of old-growth forests. Reducing these uncertainties can provide a good understanding of the carbon dynamics. This is particularly important because carbon stocks are subjected to a variety of different environmental conditions and anthropogenic disturbances (Keith et al. 2009).

The southeastern temperate forests of Australia have been categorized as the tallest and densest forests in the world (Fedrigo et al. 2014; Keith et al. 2009; Pan et al. 2013). In Victoria, the Central Highlands contains temperate forest ecosystems with tall, dense tree stands. These temperate forests can store more carbon per unit by area than tropical rainforest, with a total

biomass carbon density averaging 208 ± 131 mg C per hectare (Fedrigo et al. 2014; Pan et al. 2013). Although biomass estimates of living and dead organic materials may be accurate to 30%, these forest ecosystems contain large trees such as *Eucalyptus regnans* and *Nothofagus cunninghamii* which can store large amount of carbon (Fedrigo et al. 2014; Mackey 2014). The cool wet temperate forest is dominated by *E. regnans* (Mountain Ash). It is a giant tree from the family Myrtaceae able to growth up to 115m in height (Holliday 2002). This tree is well known for being the tallest species in Australia, the tallest flowering tree in the world, and for its highly valuable wood (Holliday 2002; Lindenmayer et al. 1993). According to Keith et al. (2009), the cool wet temperate can sequestrate around 1,867 tons of C per hectare. However, large *E. regnans* are likely to develop internal cavities due to self-pruning and self-thinning resulting in little or no branches in the lower trunks (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Lindenmayer et al. 1993). Cavity development in *E. regnans* is also likely to be related to the loss of branches due to wind and snow damage (Lindenmayer et al. 1993). Few studies have evaluated the impact of internal decomposition in *E. regnans* to the total carbon stocks (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Roxburgh et al. 2006). Some research has suggested that the signs of decay were presented in trees greater than 50cm dbh (Roxburgh et al. 2006). However, how internal decay was analyzed or assessed remains uncertain (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Roxburgh et al. 2006).

Together with the cool temperate wet forest, cool temperate rainforests also have a significant contribution in carbon stocks (Fedrigo et al. 2014). According to Fedrigo et al. (2014), rainforest carbon stocks above-ground component is 550mg per hectare and below-ground between 453–647mg per hectare. Although rainforests were the third highest in carbon stocks compared to eucalyptus (dominated by *E. regnans*) and mixed forests (*E. regnans* and other rainforest species), the density of living stems greater than 10cm dbh was significantly higher (712 ± 239 stems per hectare) than the other forest ecosystems (Fedrigo et al. 2014). The living stem density greater than 50cm in the rainforest was also significant (52 ± 23 stems per hectare; $p = 0.001$) (Fedrigo et al. 2014). In this research, the rainforest's largest tree species only represented 2%, however, 38% of the total carbon stock of the rainforest was contained in these large trees (Fedrigo et al. 2014). Large trees in the cool temperate rainforest represent an important contributor to carbon stocks of the Central Highland region. However, few studies have reported the carbon stocks for cool temperate rainforest of Victoria that includes measurements of coarse woody debris and fallen litter (Fedrigo et al. 2014; Norris, Arnold & Fairman 2010). However, little or no studies have measured the internal decay in large living trees to evaluate the biomass discounting internal decomposition in these forest ecosystems. The dimensions and significance of internal decomposition in rainforest tree species, particularly *N. cunninghamii*, also remains uncertain.

1.1. The process of internal decay/cavity

Understanding the decay process within the trunk provides important insights for estimating the volume of decay and predicting decay and cavities in large trees. Decay is a natural process in trees due to the exposition of injuries, damage or infections in the trunk, branches or roots (Shigo 1985; Shortle & Dudzik 1979). Trees cannot heal or repair injuries or damage in the trunk, branches or roots (Shigo 1985). Instead, once a tree is injured or infected, the defense mechanisms generate new tissues cells in new positions and by doing so they wall off the damage (Shigo 1985). If the tree is successful in doing so, they can resist the spread of the damage. This process has been modeled by the Compartmentalization of Decay in Trees or CODIT model (Shigo 1979). The compartmentalization process creates four walls (see Fig. 1). According to Shigo (1979) in the first wall, the weakest wall, the tree plugs upward and downward from the injury through the vertical system. In the second wall, the second weakest wall, a tangential wall of the compartments is created by the last cells following the growth ring. These walls follow each ring's growth. This process is interrupted when the sheet of ray cells go through (Shigo 1979). The third wall is the second strongest at the time of injury. The radial walls created here are discontinuous due to the variation of height, thickness and length (Shigo 1979). The fourth wall is the strongest of all. Here, the cambium forms a protective wall. The wall separates the tissue created during the injury from the new tissues develop after the injury (Shigo 1979).

Figure 1 Illustration of the CODIT model (Shigo 1979).

The last wall is particularly important for decay calculations because it creates a cylinder in which decay can develop a cone shape within the cylinder already formed, and consequently the decay continues to spread vertically (see Fig. 2) (Shigo 1979). These walls are created while chemicals are produced that can cause different colors and defects in the wood, commonly known as ring shake in the timber industry (Shigo 1977). The decay can also spread horizontally following the ring growth patterns. According to Shigo (1979), the presence of external cavities in the trunk is a result of a successful compartmentalized infection or injured.

Figure 2 (a) illustrates internal decay following by an injury in the bark. Figure (b) shows the expansion of decay vertically and horizontally within the trunk as a conical shape (Shigo 1979).

1.2. Decay/cavity impact on biomass estimates

In the literature, there is an agreement that the forest biomass calculations in large trees are being overestimated when internal decay is not accounted for (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2015). Roxburgh et al. (2006) evaluated the differences between calculating tree biomass using the regression equation developed by Ash and Helman (1990) in which internal decay is not included, and the adjustment of this equation by adding internal decomposition. Data collected from the State Forest of NSW from 527 harvested trees, demonstrated that signs of internal decay were present in trees of 50cm dbh (Roxburgh et al. 2006). Using the adjusted equation showed that the actual biomass of trees with 120cm dbh is 50% of their original estimates (Roxburgh et al. 2006). Following the equation

developed by Ash and Helman (1990), the tree biomass curve significantly increases when tree diameter is greater than 145cm dbh (“Method a”, Fig. 3). However, the curve begins to asymptote around 145cm dbh when the adjusted equation is applied “Method b”. There is a potential source of error estimating the biomass using “Method a” due to the differences after trees are greater than 150cm dbh (Roxburgh et al. 2006). According to Roxburgh et al. (2006), the adjusted equation was more conservative and therefore appropriate for calculating and reporting carbon biomass (Roxburgh et al. 2006). The findings of this research are particularly important, because theoretically, large trees can develop significant internal decay and cavities and these elements have not been added in traditional biomass equations (Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2015). Modelling adjusted biomass to internal decay in *E. regnans* is crucial to evaluate the biomass curve “method b” in which 50% of the total biomass is discounted.

Overestimation of large tree biomass is a common problem worldwide. In China, Zheng et al. (2015) assessed biomass estimates in old-growth forests where the development of decay and cavity had been overlooked. According to Zheng et al. (2015) carbon studies have mainly focused on the decomposition in fallen litter, coarse woody debris or dead trees, but ignore the decomposition that also occurs in living trees. The wood inside of the cavity can decay at a substantial rate (Zheng et al. 2015). Results suggests that although the rate of decomposition is slower than in logs and snags, it can develop large pipes or cavities within the trunk. Compared to logs and snags, cavity decomposition is lower due to low levels of moisture content. Both Zheng et al. (2015) and Roxburgh et al. (2006) have pointed out that adjustments for carbon estimations needs to include the development of cavities due to its considerable influences in the total stem biomass volume estimates.

Figure 3 Two curve showing the above-ground biomass relationship. First curve corresponds to “method a” developed by Ash and Helman (1990), in which internal decay is not included. Second curve of “method b” developed by (Roxburgh et al. 2006) shows an asymptotic curve influenced when internal decomposition is applied.

If decay/cavity development is significant in large trees, this may represent an important opportunity to evaluate how significant the decay/cavity processes is in large tree species, particularly, in the southeastern temperate forests of Victoria. A study in these areas developed a new model of biomass of *E. regnans* and showed that internal decomposition has an important impact on the carbon stored (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003). The model includes information of the growth and decay processes of large and old trees in logging coupes from Tasmania and Victoria. The main trend indicates that after the last fire (321 years ago), the carbon stored increased within the *E. regnans* stand. However, once trees reach 215 years of age, the carbon stored decreased due to thinning and decay (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003). In addition, important internal decay in old *E. regnans* stands do not always suggest a negative carbon storage loss. In undisturbed rainforest, the total carbon content balances out at 1500t C per hectare near 375 years of age. The decay of old *E. regnans* was compensated by the growth of the understorey of the rainforest (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003). Some of our study sites occur in the cool wet temperate and rainforest of the Central Highlands, however, little is known about the abundance and distribution of decay in volume or the sizes of cavities compared to the total biomass of *E. regnans* and *N. cunninghamii* species commonly found in these ecosystems. Although there are possible compensations of the carbon loss in the cavities of large trees in undisturbed forests, the main trend suggests the carbon loss caused by cavities are less likely to be compensated in disturbed forests (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003).

1.3. Horizontal and vertical spread of decay

The formation of internal decay and cavities in trees can result in a slow process that moves horizontally and vertically through the trunk resulting in large cavities (Shigo 1979; Zheng et al. 2015). Horizontally, it was found that the average of cavity development was slightly inferior to the growth rate of the tree (Zheng et al. 2015). Consequently, the tree, and the cavities, continue to grow. The vertical spread can be affected when micro-organisms such as fungi enter the trunk after infections. In most angiosperms, hyphae (fungus) move through the vascular conduits, allowing a faster vertical expansion (Zheng et al. 2015). These internal pipes can grow, in some cases, throughout the entire stem (Zheng et al. 2015). Research from British Columbia in a temperate forest conducted by Edworthy and Martin (2014) found similar rapid responses in vertical cavities in living trees 16.8mm per year vertically and 1.4mm per year horizontally. Commonly, the rate of vertical decay is faster than the horizontal (Zheng et al. 2015). Zheng et al. (2015) found that similar vertical rate of decay, but, the horizontal rate was higher than the results presented by Edworthy and Martin (2014). According to Zheng et al. (2015), the high rates of horizontal decay could possibly be linked to warmer temperatures of the study sites. Both studies agree that the sapwood seems to restrict the expansion of cavities during the decay process. These assumptions were also verified by the study, in which cavities did not progress to the sapwood (Zheng et al. 2015). Furthermore, the rate of decay can vary depending on the climate conditions and the species.

1.4. Decay/cavity and diameter

In the literature, it is recognized that decay and cavity development may be positively correlated to tree diameter due to a slow rate of wood decomposition (Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Nogueira, Nelson & Fearnside 2006; Zheng et al. 2009). Lindenmayer et al. (1993) studied around 2,315 trees both alive and dead carrying cavities in the cool temperate wet forests in the Central Highlands of Victoria in Australia. The primary eucalypts species used were *Eucalyptus obliqua*, *E. nitens*, *E. cypellocarpa*, *E. delegatensis* and *E. regnans*. The findings of this study suggest that all tree Eucalyptus species showed a positive relationship between tree diameter and the abundance of holes in stem and branches and fissures (Lindenmayer et al. 1993). Normally, large and older trees are likely to develop and be affected by cavities. Some species are more subjective to develop a specify type of cavities such as fissures which were frequently found in *E. regnans* then another species. Evidences from this study suggest cavities trees with greater diameter are likely to contain more cavities (see Fig. 4). However, diameter is not the only element related to cavity formation in living trees; species, topography, age, slope, health, type of fungus or injures can also influence the development of cavities (Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Zheng et al. 2009). Therefore, diameter together with specific environmental variables of the sites of study should be include in the evaluation of decay and cavity.

Figure 4 Percentage of trees containing cavity types by diameter. Slim trees < 2m dbh and Fat trees >2m dbh (Lindenmayer et al. 1993).

Zheng et al. (2009) evaluated the abundance and distribution of cavity development in a subtropical montane evergreen forest in China. In this research, at least 76% of living trees carrying cavities were range between 5cm to 60cm dbh. Nevertheless, the occurrence of living trees containing cavities were correlated to diameter sizes at dbh (see Fig. 5). Zheng et al. (2009) results concluded that the probability of trees carrying cavities vary among species. Although similar results were concluded in Lindenmayer et al. (1993) and Zheng et al. (2009), the methods

Figure 5 Distribution of living trees cavities across dbh categories (Zheng et al. 2009).

used to study cavities in living trees were significantly different and difficult to be compared. Zheng et al. (2015) have also identified a knowledge gap in the development of internal decay

and cavities in large trees. Some studies presented in this introduction acknowledged the formation of large proportion of decay and cavity in large trees by measuring cavities visually observed (Edworthy & Martin 2014; Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2009; Zheng et al. 2015). Although external signs of decay can provide insights of internal decomposition, decay and cavities can be located within the trunk without visual external cavities (see Fig. 6). In addition, visual assessment alone may implicate important limitations because there are uncertainties of the internal conditions of decay/cavity within the tree (Kennard, Putz & Niederhofer 1996). These unknown dimensions represent an important limitation in the carbon estimates of living and large trees.

Figure 6 Dead cavitied trunk of *N. cunninghamii* (A) and *E. regnans* (B) at the Central Highland of Victoria (Photo: Cristina Serrano).

Decomposition leading to internal and external cavity formations has gained important attention for carbon estimates and biodiversity conservation. Studies presented here have mainly developed research focuses on the abundance and distribution of external decay/cavities in tree stems with a variety of methods which provide some important insights. However, there are important issues and limitations examining internal decay/cavity in large trees in the forest. Research needs to be focused on inspections inside of the trunk to evaluate the significant influences of decay and cavity in the overall biomass stem. Therefore, modelling tree internal wood decay and cavity development to reduce uncertainties in large trees carbon estimates is fundamental. To do so, we have established the following objectives:

- 1) To determine the probability of *E. regnans* and *N. cunninghamii* to develop internal decay and cavities based on tree diameter and other environmental conditions.
- 2) To model the development and volume of internal decay and cavities of *E. regnans* and *N. cunninghamii* based on tree diameter.
- 3) To determine the impacts of accounting for internal decay and cavities on carbon stocks calculations.

2. Methods

This study was conducted in the Central Highlands of Victoria which is located around 100km from northeast of Melbourne. The site plots coincided with previous plots developed for forest carbon assessment by the School of Ecosystem and Forest Sciences at the University of Melbourne. Four sites of old-growth forests were selected from those plots: Toolangi, David Ashton, Donna Buang and Cambarville. All sites contain permanent plots with a fixed area of 40m by 10m combined with a variable radius. Each site was previously selected in two forest ecosystem types: the cool temperate wet forests dominated by *E. regnans* and rainforest in which *N. cunninghamii* is commonly found. The selection of trees was based on a representative diameter distribution. Previous diameter measurements were used to locate and select the samples and ensure a diameter range across the plots. Trees less than 20cm dbh were discarded because the development of decay/cavity was less likely to occur in these trees (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2009).

2.1. Fieldwork measurements

The detection of decayed wood and cavity was diagnosed by applying two assessments. First, decayed wood was measured by drilling through the bark of the trees using the instrument IML-Resistograph Drill (IML Power Drill) (see Fig. 7). This device can easily identify and quantify decay defects and the absence of wood by drilling into the cambium with a drilling needle 40cm long (Bethge, Mattheck & Hunger 1996; Johnstone et al. 2010). The tip of this needle is 3mm wide and the shaft is 1.5mm in diameter (Bethge, Mattheck & Hunger 1996).

Figure 7 IML-Resistograph Drill (IML Power Drill) in the fieldwork (Photo: Cristina Serrano).

The internal decay/cavities were also assessed by combining the readings from the resistograph and the CODIT model (Johnstone et al. 2007; Johnstone et al. 2010). The used of these methods to assess wood decay by using the resistograph has showed a strong level of accuracy to predict internal decomposition (Johnstone et al. 2007). A research conducted by Johnstone et al. (2007) used the IML- Resistograph Drill combined with the CODIT model to predict the amount of wood decay in 17 tree samples of *Eucalyptus praecox*, *E. radiata* and *E. globulus*. After measuring the samples, Johnstone et al. (2007) harvested the trees and compared the area predicted using the resistograph and the CODIT model to the actual decay present in the cross-section. Results suggest a significant level of precision between the areas decayed predicted and the actual decayed area (see Appendix. a). The device overestimated 7 tree samples and underestimated one tree sample (Johnstone et al. 2010). Although tree diameter was relatively small, the level of precision in predicting decay was significantly important. The study concluded that the resistograph can be a reliable device as a part of the CODIT model to predict wood decay.

Second, the collection of data was also based on visually assessed (see Appendix. b). Each tree profile contains the evaluation of visual signs of decay such as the presence or absence of conks, blind-conks, burls, forks, rotten top, scars and external cavities. Other environmental variables measured were slope, landscape position, amplitude and the vitality assessment. The visual assessment is important to evaluate the relationship between the external signs of decay/cavity vs. the internal decay/cavity for future predictions.

2.2. Decay/cavity estimates

The resistograph readings were recorded in the form of a trance graph (see Appendix c). This graph has two curves; the green curve is the drill force in which the drill needle rotates inside the trunk and is clamped into the drilling channel (IML 2012). This creates shaft friction. The blue curve is the feed force that pushes the drill needle into the trunk (IML 2012). This force is less influenced by the shaft friction which helps to facilitate the decay assessment (IML 2012). Both curves were used to evaluate the internal decomposition to 40cm deep. Commonly, internal decay is assessed in three stages related to the amplitude percentage of the trance graph. When the curves of this graph are below 10%, this indicates an advanced decay or cavity. When the curve drops slightly between 10% and 20%, this indicates early decay, also named incipient decay (IML 2013). These parameters of decay are usually used when the average of the curve in the trance graph is between 40% and 55% (IML 2013). Consequently, higher amplitude in the graph indicates more resistance and sound-wood (IML 2013). A lower or sudden drop in the amplitude shows a change in the wood structure and strength, which indicates decay or cavities (IML 2013). Some adjusted decay/cavity parameters were made in our tree species due to the differing wood density (see Appendix d). The internal decay found by the resistograph equaling less than 1cm in length was not recorded to avoid possible errors (Johnstone et al. 2007). The free-floating wood, which is decayed wood hanging in the cavities, were counted as advanced decay. Normally, the free-floating wood is assessed as cavity, however, for the purposes of this research free floating is still counted as wood that contains carbon.

Diagrams with the measured location of decay/cavity were developed in each cross-section at each height using AUTOCAD to estimate the area of decay/cavity in complete or incomplete profiles. In the case of complete profiles, the overlapping decay/cavity was discounted to avoid over-estimations, and then the area and percentage of decay/cavity were estimated. When the profiles were incomplete, a systematic method was developed in which the area not measured by the resistograph was estimated base on the ending of each drill and distributed equally in the central area not measured. For instance, the drills of an incomplete profile of a *N. cunninghamii* (Tree ID: DBRFNC12) of 106.6cm at 0.3m showed early decay at the end of two drills (50%), another drill ended in advanced decay (25%) and one last drill ended in sound-wood (25%). The drill cross-sections of 1.3m (106.6cm) and 1.8m height (97.3cm) ended in cavity, therefore, the central area not measured will be 100% cavity (see Appendix e). The diameter of this central area was measured by discounting 80cm diameter of the resistograph measurement from the diameter of the tree. Then the areas measured and the central area not measured were summed up to determinate the final area of decay or cavity of the cross-section.

We examined the relationship between the development of decay/cavity and diameter through binary logistical regression analyses using R version 3.3.1. The relationship between the area estimate of decay/cavity and diameter was analyzed by polynomial and exponential regressions in Excel 2016 and Minitab 7. We also examined how environmental variables can enhance the prediction of decay/cavity development through binary logistical regressions and step-wise regression. Three different models were developed to evaluate these relationships. First, the probability of decay/cavity in contrast to diameter; second, the probability of decay/cavity in relationship to diameter and environmental variables; and third, the probability of decay/cavity in relationship to diameter and the presence or absence of environmental variables.

2.3. Decay/cavity volume and biomass

The volume was estimated based on the area estimate of decay/cavity. The CODIT model suggests that in the vertical spread of internal decomposition, wall no.4 creates a cone shape within a cylinder. Two cone figures were used to estimate the volume of decay/cavity. First, a tapered cone from 0.3m up to 1.3m and from 1.8m a cone figure was calculated (see Fig. 8). In the case that the area of the top portion was higher than the lower portion, a cone shape was calculated. The following cone tapered equation was used:

$$V_{\text{tapered cone}} = \frac{1}{3} \pi * (r1^2 + r1 * r2 + r2^2) * H$$

For the calculations of the tapered cone, the radius of the formula corresponds to the radius of decay (r1, r2) and the height was 1m which is the distance between the two drills (H= 0.3m -1.3m = 1m). In the case of the cone, the radius of decay and the height from 0.3m and 1.3m was known. However, the total height of decay pocket and the angle of the two triangle figures was not (see Fig. 9). The following equations were used to estimate the volume of decay as a cone shape:

$$\text{Angle } \alpha = \text{tangent}(\alpha) = \frac{h}{(R - r)}$$

$$\arctan(\tan(\alpha)) = \alpha$$

$$\tan(\alpha) = \frac{H}{R}$$

$$H = \tan(\alpha) \cdot R$$

Figure 8 Components of the tapered cone to calculate the volume between 0.3 and 1.3 heights.

Figure 9 Components of a cone to calculate the volume from 1.8m. Red color indicates unknown data while green color shows the data known.

$$V_{\text{cono}} = \frac{1}{3} \pi * R^2 * H$$

The angle (α) was calculated by the decay pocket height (1.3m-1.8m) and radius of (R,r) both heights. To measure the total height of the pocket of decay, the angle was multiplied by the radius of decay (R). The allometric equations to calculate the total biomass of *E. regnans* was developed by Dean & Roxburgh (2006). This equation was established for the stem volume as a function of dbh using a sample of 24 trees. This equation includes a maximum height of 120m supported by previously recorded heights for this species (Dean & Roxburgh 2006). The basic density value of *E. regnans* was 482.93kg/m³ (Ilic et al. 2000). The following equations were used:

$$\text{Volume } V_{(s)} = 1100 \left(1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{DBH}{9.2} \right)^2 \right)^{-1} \right) R^2 = 0.95, \text{RMSE} = 34.2\text{m}^3$$

$$\text{Bark mass} = (0.112/0.816) * \text{stem mass}$$

$$\text{Branch mass} = (0.066/0.816) * \text{stem mass}$$

$$\text{Leave mass} = (0.004/0.816) * \text{stem mass}$$

The $V_{(s)}$ is the volume in m³ and the dbh is in meters. RMSE stands for the root mean squared error which was used to test different taper curves (Dean & Roxburgh 2006). Thus, RMSE plot increases when dbh increases. To evaluate different equations independently of the tree sizes, RMSE was divided for each curve to provide a relative RMSE (Dean & Roxburgh 2006).

For *N. cunninghamii*, there were no allometric equations available for the species. As an alternative, a previously developed equation for *N. menziesii* was selected due to its close phylogenetic relationship to *N. cunninghamii* (Jordan & Hill 1999). In a study from New Zealand, allometric equations for several species including *N. menziesii* were developed for estimating carbon stocks (Beets et al. 2012). The following allometric equations were used:

$$\text{Stem and branches } \geq 10\text{cm Volume (m}^3/\text{tree): } Y = (6.18 * 10^{-5}) * (DBH^2 * H)^{0.968}$$

$$\text{Stem and branches } \geq 10\text{cm Carbon (kg/tree): } Y = (0.0256 * 10^{-5}) * (DBH^2 * H)^{0.936}$$

$$\text{Branch } < 10\text{cm Carbon (kg/tree): } Y = (0.0220 * 10^{-5}) * (DBH^2 * H)^{0.936}$$

$$\text{Foliage Carbon (kg/tree): } Y = (0.0474 * 10^{-5}) * (DBH^2 * H)^{1.595}$$

These equations include the stem and large branches, small branches and the foliage biomass. The dbh is the diameter at breast height and H corresponds to the height (Beets et al. 2012). The basic density for *N. cunninghamii* was 577.3 kg/m³ (Ilic et al. 2000).

3. Results

A total of 43 trees were sampled in which 21 were *E. regnans* and 22 were *N. cunninghamii*. The percentage of decayed wood in the cross-section shows that early decay is present in all trees regardless of tree diameter, however, early decay is significantly greater with trees that are greater than 250cm dbh. Advanced decay increases with diameter up to 250cm dbh, however, it decreases slightly when trees are greater than 250cm dbh. The cavities increase with tree diameter. According to our estimates, the percentage of decay and cavities are distributed in all tree diameters with an increase when trees surpass 200cm dbh (see Fig. 10).

Figure 10 Decay and cavity formation in the cross-section of *E. regnans* at dbh.

The percentage of decay/cavity in *N. cunninghamii* has a clear trend. The percentage of early decay in the cross-section at dbh decreased significantly when diameter increased. The advanced decay also increased with diameter, however, when trees were greater than 150cm dbh advanced decay was less compared to the high percentage of cavities. There was a significant increase of cavity percentage when diameter increased, particularly after 150cm dbh (see Fig. 11).

Figure 11 Decay and cavity formation in the cross-section of *E. regnans* at dbh class.

3.1. Probability of decay/cavity

The first model developed was to predict the probability of decay/cavity to occur as tree diameter increased. The results of the logistic regressions suggest that there was not a significant relationship between decay/cavity and diameter in *E. regnans*. This species presents at least some stage of decay/cavity formation regardless of the diameter sizes. Therefore, the probability of *E. regnans* developing decay/cavity is not restricted to diameter. Similar results were found for *N. cunninghamii* related to early decay in all heights and advanced decay at 0.3m and 1.8m high. However, a strong relationship was found between advanced decay and diameter at dbh ($p = 0.0316$, $n = 22$). The relationship between cavity and diameter was also strong for all heights. Therefore, the probability of *N. cunninghamii* developing cavities may be significantly related to the increase of diameter (see. Fig. 12).

Figure 12 Prediction models curve of *N. cunninghamii* to develop cavity related to diameter.

No significant relationship was found between the probability of decay/cavity and the environmental variables in the step-wise and binary logistic regression. However, the polynomial regressions showed a strong relationship between diameter and internal decomposition (see Fig. 13). When dbh increased, the estimated area of internal decomposition also increased. The results were also strong when the variables were analyzed separately. Early decay presented $R^2 = 0.9406$, $n = 20$. However, when internal decay was evaluated separately, the exponential regressions showed to fit better when it was applied to advanced decay ($R^2 = 0.5135$, $n = 15$).

Figure 13 Estimated Area of Cavity and Internal decomposition (cavity + decay) in *E. regnans*.

Compared to *E. regnans*, *N. cunninghamii* also showed a significant relationship between the estimated area of internal decomposition (decay and cavity) and dbh (see Fig. 14). In contrast to

E. regnans, the decay and the stage of decay separately did not show any definite relationship. For early decay, $R^2 = 0.0088$, $n = 14$, while advanced decay $R^2 = 0.2809$, $n = 21$.

Figure 14 Estimated Area of Cavity and Internal decomposition (cavity + decay) in *N. cunninghamii*.

3.2. The volume of internal decomposition

The visual assessment recorded in the bark was not necessarily a reliable source to accurately predict the stage of decay without reaching the center of the tree due to their large sizes. However, our systematic method to estimate the total area of decay/cavity did not fit with a tree in which the visual assessment was a reliable source. To evaluate the differences, the reliable visual assessment for one *E. regnans* was applied, resulting in a significant difference in the volume. For instance, this individual tree of 401.5cm dbh contains a large cone shape cavity in the center of the base up to 4.5m height (see Appendix. f). For this tree, the systematic method to estimate the total area of decay/cavity did not fit with the actual visual assessment. In our systematic method to estimate the total decay/cavity area, the center would have been assessed as advanced decay because most of the drills ended with this decay, however, it was assumed to be a cavity due to the visual assessment in which the sizes and location of the main cavity was known. As can be seen from the graphs, the volume of decay of this tree is significantly low, measuring approximately 0.033m^3 . However, the volume of cavity was approximately 22.6m^3 (see Fig. 15). Therefore, the center of the tree was assessed as a cavity.

Figure 15 The volume of decay and cavity estimated for *E. regnans*.

For the remaining trees of both species, it is assumed that the method in which the area was estimated fit to what we can measure from the resistograph readings. In the case of *N. cunninghamii*, the development of cavity tends to increase for trees greater than 100m, as well as the volume of cavity. However, the volume of decay tends to decrease due to large cavities (see Fig. 16).

Figure 16 The volume of decay and cavity estimated for *N. cunninghamii*.

3.3. Impact on carbon stocks

The overall aboveground biomass of *E. regnans* that was adjusted to the volume of internal decomposition decreased slightly compared to the biomass with no internal decay or cavity (see Fig. 17). The biomass of the trees sampled showed small differences between original and adjusted biomass when trees were between 30cm and 100cm dbh (n = 21). However, when tree diameter increased, the differences between the two biomass estimates increased resulting in a slight decrease in the total adjusted biomass due to internal decay and cavity.

Figure 17 Total tree biomass of *E. regnans* estimated in this research project using *E. regnans* allometric equations developed by (Dean & Roxburgh 2006). Black dotted curve indicates the biomass with no internal decomposition. Gray dotted curve corresponds to the adjusted biomass in which internal decomposition was discounted.

When the adjusted biomass estimates were applied to a stand of 94 *E. regnans* of the cool temperate forest of the four sites, the same patterns were found compared to our tree samples (see Fig. 18). When trees overpass 150cm dbh, the differences between the original biomass and adjusted biomass increases, resulting in a relative small decrease in the adjusted biomass estimate of the stand.

Similar to the results of *E. regnans* biomass, the total biomass of the tree samples and the stand of *N. cunninghamii* showed a slight decrease when trees were greater than 100cm dbh (tree samples = 22; stand = 141) (See fig. 19). This is a relative decrease of the estimated biomass of the trees and stand when the adjusted biomass is applied.

Figure 18 Total stand tree biomass of *E. regnans* estimated in this research project using *E. regnans* allometric equations developed by (Dean & Roxburgh 2006). Black dotted curve indicates the biomass with no internal decomposition. Orange dotted curve corresponds to the adjusted biomass in which internal decomposition was discounted.

Figure 19 Total tree biomass of *N. cunninghamii* estimated in this research project using *N. menziesii* allometric equations developed by (Beets et al. 2012). Black dotted curve indicates the biomass with no decay. Gray dotted curve shows the adjusted biomass of the tree sample and orange dotted curve is the adjusted biomass of the stand discounting internal decomposition.

The carbon stocks of the stand of the four study sites shows a decrease of the biomass when the adjustments of internal decay are applied. This internal decomposition includes decay and cavity together. Although there is a decrease, the differences are relative small (see Table. 1)

Table 1 Carbon stocks (Mg ha⁻¹) in aboveground components of Cool temperate wet forest and rainforest of the Central Highlands of Victoria, Australia. MA = Cool temperate wet forest (*E. regnans*), RF = Cool temperate rainforest (*N. cunninghamii*), CV = Cambarville, DA = David Ashton, DB = Donna Buang, TW = Toolangi.

PLOT ID	<i>E. regnans</i> (n = 94)		<i>N. Cunninghamii</i> (n = 141)		Total	
	Biomass No Decay	Biomass Adjusted	Biomass No Decay	Biomass Adjusted	Biomass No Decay	Biomass Adjusted
CV_MA	1310.90	1256.14	24.87	25.44	1335.76	1281.59
CV_RF	228.44	223.61	2091.31	1997.83	2319.75	2221.44
DA_MA	1911.56	1828.49	109.30	111.52	2020.85	1940.02
DA_RF	514.16	500.02	788.97	773.61	1303.12	1273.63
DB_MA	1108.29	1074.01	0.00	0.00	1108.29	1074.01
DB_RF	149.57	143.79	500.55	488.32	650.12	632.11
TW_MA	1082.58	1058.32	0.00	0.00	1082.58	1058.32
TW_RF	37.85	36.51	420.23	410.77	458.07	447.29

4. Discussion

4.1. Internal decomposition and diameter

The results of this study along with other studies have showed that the relationship between internal cavity and diameter is significantly strong (Edworthy & Martin 2014; Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Roxburgh et al. 2006; Zheng et al. 2009; Zheng et al. 2015). Although the rate of internal decomposition of *E. regnans* and *N. cunninghamii* was not part of the objectives of this research, the estimated area of cavity by cross-section increases when tree diameter increases. In terms of prediction, the internal decay showed to be more variable than the cavities across the diameter distribution in both species. In other words, there was some proportion of decay (early or advanced) in almost all trees regardless of the diameter sizes. Therefore, the relationship between the internal decay and diameter was not significant. The internal decay can be presented in trees with small and large diameters. Some studies have suggested that the internal decomposition can potentially be important in large trees, particularly in *E. regnans* (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Roxburgh et al. 2006). However, the area estimated by cross-section of internal decay and results of logistic regressions of *E. regnans* suggests an important variation. Therefore, we cannot conclude that internal decay is necessarily related to diameter sizes due to these strong variations in the results of *E. regnans*.

4.2. Internal decomposition and environmental conditions

Fewer studies has evaluated how environmental conditions influence the development of decay/cavity in large trees. Lindenmayer et al., (1993) surveyed key environmental attributes such as stand age, slope, aspect, radiation, latitude, longitude, elevation and topographic position. The results from this research showed that cavity formation in Eucalypts in the cool temperate forests of southeastern of Victoria vary depending on this environmental factors (Lindenmayer et al. 1993). The cavities were more likely to be found in sites with steep slopes, higher latitudes in the southern region of the study area and in sites in which trees were younger than 50 years old (Lindenmayer et al. 1993). However, our results suggest that the environmental external conditions of the four sites such as scars, external cavities, slope, altitude, conks or vitality did not have significant influence on the develop of internal decay/cavity.

4.3. Internal decomposition volume based on diameter

The resistograph as an instrument has important limitations for determining the volume of decay and cavity in large stems. The lowest dbh of *E. regnans* was 31.8cm dbh and the largest was 401.5cm dbh. In the case of *N. cunninghamii*, the lowest dbh was 20.4cm and the largest was 237cm. For most part, the central area of the cross-sections was not recorded by the resistograph due to the limitation of the 40m of length of the drill needle. To assess the possible internal decomposition in the center of the stem (if there was any), a systematic method was developed based on the ends of the drills. This method was based on the CODIT model. However, there is a high risk of over or under-estimating the decay in large trees without reaching the center of the stem just by relying on the drill device. Visual assessment was incorporated where it was possible to enhance the central area not measured. However, it was used to evaluate what may be expected inside of the tree (decay or cavity) rather than using this information to incorporate it in the total estimated area of decay/cavity. There was only one case in which the visual assessment

was incorporated as part of the estimated area of cavity. The tree developed a large cavity in the base up to 4.5m height (Tree ID: DAMAMA05). Using the visual assessment, the results showed an important discrepancy in the total area of cavity. Visual assessment has been used to predict internal decay, however, it provides limitations for the accuracy of internal decay and the conditions inside the tree (Kennard, Putz & Niederhofer 1996).

4.4. Decomposing biomass and carbon stocks

The factor of internal decomposition developed in this study for *E. regnans* and *N. cunninghamii* shows relatively small values, $R^2 = 0.2964$ for *E. regnans* and $R^2 = 0.2604$ for *N. cunninghamii* (see Appendix. g). In order to evaluate the impact of the estimated decay/cavity volume to the total carbon stocks of the stand, the factors estimated for *E. regnans* in this study were compared to the factors developed in other studies by Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey (2003) and Roxburgh et al. (2006) (see Fig. 20).

Figure 20 Total stand biomass of *E. regnans* estimated by us compared to the adjusted biomass estimated by (Roxburgh et al. 2006). Black curve corresponds to the biomass with no decay. Orange curve shows the adjusted biomass developed for us. Gray curve shows the adjusted biomass developed by (Roxburgh et al. 2006).

The stand adjusted biomass of *E. regnans* (n = 94) showed a significant discrepancy compared to Roxburgh et al. (2003) adjusted biomass estimates (see Fig. 21). (Roxburgh et al. 2006). Regardless of the internal decomposition, the biomass of the three curves started to show visible differences when trees were greater than 50cm dbh. However, when trees were greater than 100cm dbh, the adjusted biomass developed in this research (orange curve) shows a relatively small difference compared to the original biomass (black curve), and a significant discrepancy compared to the adjusted biomass (gray curve) developed by Roxburgh et al. (2006). Roxburgh et al. (2006) developed an adjusted factor in which 0.5 was given to trees greater than 120cm dbh due to internal decomposition. In other

Figure 21 Total tree biomass for *E. regnans* developed by (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003). Black curve indicates tree biomass with no decay. Orange curve corresponds to the adjusted biomass estimated by (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003). Gray curve indicates the adjusted biomass developed by (Roxburgh et al. 2006).

the research (orange curve) shows a relatively small difference compared to the original biomass (black curve), and a significant discrepancy compared to the adjusted biomass (gray curve) developed by Roxburgh et al. (2006). Roxburgh et al. (2006) developed an adjusted factor in which 0.5 was given to trees greater than 120cm dbh due to internal decomposition. In other

words, trees greater than 120cm dbh may loss 50% of the total biomass. Our assessments of the development of internal decay and cavity of 21 *E. regnans* showed a relative small adjustment factor for trees greater than 120cm dbh at 0.98 ($R^2 = 0.2964$).

The factor of internal decomposition for *E. regnans* was also compared to the adjusted factor developed by (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003). Their findings suggest that the internal decomposition factor in trees over 120cm dbh is 1 (see Table. 2). Our factors have similar results up to trees with 190cm dbh. However, when trees are greater than that, the biomass loss increases up to 0.5 when trees are 250cm dbh, resulting in similar factors as the those estimated by Roxburgh et al. (2006).

The discrepancy of these results in the factor of the internal decomposition may have important implications in the total carbon biomass estimates (see Appendix h). Particularly, when there is a lack of information and research of the development of decay and cavity in large *E. regnans*. Although Roxburgh et al. (2006) argues that the internal decomposition in large trees can be substantial for carbon estimates, no details are given of the significance in the decay and cavity development within living and large trees. Roxburgh et al. (2006) points out that data collected by States Forests of New South Wales from 527 harvested trees show signs of decay when trees were approximately 50cm dbh. However, little is known of the sizes of the trees used to estimate the internal

Table 2 Internal decomposition factor for estimating adjusted biomass of *E. regnans* by Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey (2003); Roxburgh et al. (2006) and our research project.

DBH	Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey (2003) Decay Factor	Roxburgh et al. (2006) Decay Factor	Carbon Project (2016) Decay Factor
30	1.00	1	1.03
40	1.00	1.00	1.02
50	1.00	0.99	1.01
60	1.00	0.91	1.00
70	1.00	0.84	1.00
80	1.00	0.77	0.99
90	1.00	0.69	0.99
100	1.00	0.62	0.98
110	1.00	0.54	0.98
120	1.00	0.50	0.98
130	1.00	0.50	0.97
150	0.99	0.50	0.97
170	0.98	0.50	0.96
190	0.95	0.50	0.96
210	0.88	0.50	0.96
230	0.75	0.50	0.95
250	0.55	0.50	0.95
270	0.50	0.50	0.95
290	0.50	0.50	0.94
310	0.50	0.50	0.94
330	0.50	0.50	0.94
350	0.50	0.50	0.94
370	0.50	0.50	0.94
390	0.50	0.50	0.93

decomposition factors. No information is provided of what biomass components are incorporated in the internal decomposition factors (stem, branches, roots, foliage). Whether or not there was access to the trunk to examine and measure the development of decay and cavity of these trees remains unknown (Roxburgh et al. 2006). Furthermore, if the environmental conditions of New South Wales may have a significant influence on the development of decay and cavity in those trees is also unknown (Roxburgh et al. 2006). The relationship between environmental factors and the development of decay and cavity is still unknown. For instance, a study conducted by Zheng et al. (2015) found different rates of horizontal decay expansion potentially related to warmer climate in tropical forests in China compared to temperate forest in Canada (Edworthy & Martin 2014). Additionally, Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey (2003) also points out a significant influence of decay resulting in biomass decrease, however, little is known about how the measurement of the development of decay and cavity was carried out.

4.5. Further research

The resistograph as a decay inspector device has important advantages. The cost is relatively low; it is portable and it is relatively fast at measuring decay, suggesting that more trees can potentially be sampled to enhance internal decomposition assessment. However, the resistograph device and the visual assessment alone has limitations for determining the area of decay/cavity in large trees. The uncertainty of the extent of internal decomposition can be enhance by using other devices that can also detect internal decay. Although the resistograph has been shown to have a significant level of accuracy in small and medium trees, large trees may need other devices to complement the internal decomposition inspection. Some of those devices could be the Picus, a device that can computerize tomography inside trunk (Johnstone et al. 2007). Although it may require algorithmic equations, this device can potentially be reliable in Eucalypts and easy to interpret. However, the relative cost may be high (Johnstone et al. 2007). The maximum height to drill in this research was selected due to the materials available. The results of the diagrams of each cross-section at the three different heights (0.3m, 1.3m, 1.8m) has showed that the internal decomposition had be connected to the different heights. In order words, if there were cavities assessed by the resistograph at 0.3m, it was expected to see the cavities in the other heights. Therefore, drilling up to 1.8m can potentially enhance the calculations of the volume and evaluate the vertical extension of the internal decomposition, however, this may require climbing the tree which can potentially increase risk as well as the cost of the research.

Few research has focused on assessing internal decay and cavity development in large trees. Some have incorporated internal decay and cavity development into the carbon stock estimates (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Roxburgh et al. 2006). However, little or no information is provided related to the methods used to evaluate the internal decomposition in large living trees (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Roxburgh et al. 2006). Furthermore, the decay and cavity factors to estimate the biomass discounting internal decay and cavity needs further research. Particularly, in understanding the reasons of the discrepancy in the biomass estimates that includes internal decomposition.

5. Conclusions

Our findings correlated with other studies in which the formation of cavity is strongly related to the diameter (Edworthy & Martin 2014; Lindenmayer et al. 1993; Zheng et al. 2009; Zheng et al. 2015). This is particularly clear in *N. cunninghamii* which has a greater probability of developing large internal cavities due to the increment of diameter. However, the development of internal decay (early and advanced stages) is more variable in both species which limits the capacity to predict at what particularly diameter size one could expect a proportion of decay in large trees. The wide range of environmental factors and attributes in which these two species grow limit our evaluation of how they influence the formation of internal decay/cavity. Further research is need to evaluate if environmental factors or particularly attributes of each species have a significant impact on the formation of internal decomposition. Consequently, visual assessment of the trunk, particularly external scars and cavities also limits the assessment of internal decay/cavity in large trees due to their large sizes in diameter. The visual assessment of external decay and the

detection of internal decay/cavity from the resistograph can be enhanced by using an additional device (Picus) that could potentially reach the center of the tree.

Lastly, enhancing our capacity to detect internal decay/cavity in the cool temperate wet forest and rainforest can potentially reduce the uncertainties of biomass loss in large trees due to internal decomposition. The biomass of the sites was estimated by calculating the conical volume. According to the CODIT model, the compartmentalization process that a tree active after injuries forms a conical shape of internal decay. These assumptions were used to estimate the volume and the biomass of the stand of the four study sites. Our findings suggest an important discrepancy of the total biomass of the cool temperate wet forests compared to other studies that includes decay in the biomass calculations (Dean, Roxburgh & Mackey 2003; Roxburgh et al. 2006). Particularly, the assumption that internal decay may compromise 50% of the biomass of large tree species such as *E. regnans* after 120cm dbh (Roxburgh et al. 2006). Further research is need to evaluate the possible reasons of these discrepancies. However, this research provides significant insights of the proportion and the amount of internal decay/cavity development in two important large contributor species for carbon stocks in the southeastern cool temperate forests of Victoria.

References

- Amacher, GS, Ollikainen, M & Uusivuori, J 2014, 'Forests and ecosystem services: outlines for new policy options', *Forest Policy and Economics*, vol. 47, pp.1-3.
- Ash, J & Helman, C 1990, 'Floristics and vegetation biomass of a forest catchment Kioloa, south coastal New South Wales', *Cunninghamia*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp.167-182.
- Beets, PN, Kimberley, MO, Oliver, GR, Pearce, SH, Graham, JD & Brandon, A 2012, 'Allometric equations for estimating carbon stocks in natural forest in New Zealand', *Forests*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp.818-839.
- Bethge, K, Mattheck, C & Hunger, E 1996, 'Equipment for detection and evaluation of incipient decay in trees', *Arboricultural Journal*, vol. 20, no.1, pp.13-37.
- Canadell, JG & Raupach, MR 2008, 'Managing forests for climate change mitigation', *Science*, vol. 320, no. 5882, pp.1456-1457.
- Dean, C, Roxburgh, S & Mackey, BG 2003, 'Growth modelling of eucalyptus regnans for carbon accounting at the landscape scale' in A Amaro, D Reed & P Soares (eds), *Modelling forest systems*, USA, pp.27-39.
- Dean, C & Roxburgh, S 2006, 'Improving visualisation of mature, high-carbon-sequestering forests', *Forest Biometry Modelling and Information Sciences*, vol. 1, pp.48-69.
- Kennard, DK, Putz, FE & Niederhofer, M 1996, 'The predictability of tree decay based on visual assessments', *Journal of Arboriculture*, vol. 22, pp.249-254.
- Edworthy, AB & Martin, K 2014, 'Long-term dynamics of the characteristics of tree cavities used for nesting by vertebrates', *Forest Ecology and Management*, vol. 334, pp.122-128.
- Fedrigo, M, Kasel, S, Bennett, LT, Roxburgh, SH & Nitschke, CR 2014, 'Carbon stocks in temperate forests of south-eastern Australia reflect large tree distribution and edaphic conditions', *Forest Ecology and Management*, vol. 334, pp.129-143.
- Harris, RW 2004, *Arboriculture: integrated management of landscape trees, shrubs, and vines*, 4th edition, Prentice Hall, pp. 592.
- Holliday, I 2002, *A field guide to Australian trees*, Frenchs Forest, N.S.W, New Holland, pp.328.
- IML 2013, *IML resi testing standard, procedures and audit*, IML Australia, viewed 15th October 2016 < <http://www.imlaustralia.com>>
- IML 2012, *Measured variables of the iml-resi powerdrill*, IML North America, viewed 15th October 2016 < <http://www.iml-na.com>>
- Johnstone, DM, Ades, PK, Moore, GM & Smith, IW 2007, 'Predicting wood decay in eucalypts using an expert system and the iml-resistograph drill', *Arboriculture and Urban Forestry*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 76.

- Johnstone, D, Tausz, M, Moore, G & Nicolas, M 2010, 'Quantifying wood decay in Sydney bluegum (*eucalyptus saligna*) trees', *Journal of Arboriculture*, vol. 36, no. 6, p.243-252.
- Jordan, GJ & Hill, RS 1999, 'The phylogenetic affinities of nothofagus (nothofagaceae) leaf fossils based on combined molecular and morphological data', *International Journal of Plant Sciences*, vol. 160, no. 6, pp.1177-1188.
- Keith, H, Mackey, BG & Lindenmayer, DB 2009, 'Re-evaluation of forest biomass carbon stocks and lessons from the world's most carbon-dense forests', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 106, no. 28, pp. 11635-11640.
- Kersten, W & Schwarze, FW 2005, 'Development of decay in the sapwood of trees wounded by the use of decay detecting devices', *Arboricultural Journal*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 165-181.
- Lindenmayer, DB, Cunningham, RB, Donnelly, CF, Tanton, MT & Nix, HA 1993, 'The abundance and development of cavities in Eucalyptus trees: a case study in the montane forests of Victoria, southeastern Australia'. *Forest Ecology and Management*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp.77-104.
- Ilic, J, Boland, D, McDonald, M, Downes, G & Blakemore, P 2000, *Woody density phase 1-state of knowledge*. Australian Greenhouse Office, Australia, viewed 12nd October 2016 <<http://www.fullcam.com>>
- Mackey, B 2014, 'Counting trees, carbon and climate change', *Significance*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp.19-23.
- Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2005, *Ecosystems and human well-being: synthesis*, Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. Island Press, Washington, DC, viewed 1st August 2016 <<http://www.millenniumassessment.org>>
- Nogueira, EM, Nelson, B.W & Fearnside, PM 2006, 'Volume and biomass of trees in central Amazonia: influence of irregularly shaped and hollow trunks', *Forest Ecology and Management*, vol. 227, no. 1, pp. 14-21.
- Norris, J, Arnold, S & Fairman, T 2010, 'An indicative estimate of carbon stocks on Victoria's publicly managed land using the fullcam carbon accounting model', *Australian Forestry*, vol. 73, no. 4, pp.209-219.
- Pan, Y, Birdsey, RA, Phillips, OL & Jackson, RB 2013, 'The structure, distribution, and biomass of the world's forests', *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, vol. 44, no.1, pp.593-622.
- Roxburgh, SH, Wood, SW, Mackey, BG, Woldendorp, G & Gibbons, P 2006, 'Assessing the carbon sequestration potential of managed forests: a case study from temperate Australia', *Journal of Applied Ecology*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp.1149-1159.
- Shigo, AL 1979, 'Tree decay an expanded concept', *United States Department of Agriculture Forest Service*, no. 419, pp. 73.

- Shigo, AL 1985, 'Compartmentalization of decay in trees', *Scientific American*, vol. 252, no. 4, pp. 96.
- Shortle, WC & Dudzik, KR 1979, 'Detection of decay in trees', *Journal of Arboriculture*, vol. 5, no. 10, pp. 227.
- Zheng, Z, Zhang, S, Yang, G, Tang, Y, Baskin, J, Baskin, C & Yang, L 2009, 'Abundance and distribution of cavity trees in an old-growth subtropical montane evergreen broad-leaved forest', *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp.2234-2245.
- Zheng, Z, Zhang, S, Baskin, C, Baskin, J, Schaefer, D, Yang, X & Yang, L 2015, 'Hollows in living trees develop slowly but considerably influence the estimate of forest biomass', *Functional Ecology*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 830–838.

Appendices

Appendix a.

Graph A; prediction of the location of decay using the resistograph compared to the actual decay from the cross-sections of 56 trees ($P < 0.0001$, $r^2 = 0.3003$) (Johnstone et al. 2007). Graph B; prediction of the total decayed area estimated compared to the total area of decay from the three cross sections of *Eucalyptus globulus* subsp. *Pseudoglobulus* of a total of 17 trees ($P < 0.0001$, $r^2 = 0.7584$) (Johnstone et al. 2007).

Appendix b.

Some visual assessment was scars and cavities such as the *E. regnans* in image (a). Burls in the barks like in this *N. cunninghamii* in image (b), blind conks like this *N. cunninghamii* in image (c) and dead or broken top like this *E. regnans* in image (d).

Appendix c.

The image A corresponds to the trace graph of a *N. cunninghamii* of 57.8cm dbh showing two early decay (Tree ID: TWRFNC13W2). The image B corresponds to an *E. regnans* of 262cm at 1.8m indicating two cavities and an advanced decay of a free-floating wood (Tree ID: TWMAMA20S3). Note that bark or wood reaction of decay was included as soundwood to facility the decay/cavity assessment.

Appendix d.

Stages	Definitions	<i>E. regnans</i> <i>N. cunninghamii</i>
Sound Wood	<p>Sound-wood is defined as solid wood which contains carbon.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bark is included in the sound-wood. It is at the beginning of the graph usually 2 to 2.5cm and shows low amplitude. • To simplify, reaction wood that may occur after decay is also included as sound-wood. • Sound-wood is identified when curves are consistent to the average of the trance graph. 	<p>Depends on the average amplitude of the trance graph.</p>
Early Decay	<p>Early decay is the wood in the early stages of decay, without structural strength.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The amplitude of the trance graph will decrease slightly. • There is not structural strength. 	<p>20-10% (Average amplitude 40-55%) - 7-13% (average amplitude 10-30% or average below)</p>
Advanced Decay	<p>A clear change in structure is defined as advanced decay (Harris et al, 2004; Johnstone et al. 2007). This stage also contains carbon.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decayed wood will be identified when the amplitude of the feed force, and commonly the drill resistance of the resistograph decrease significantly. • Wood is very soft. • If there is free floating wood, it would be assessed as advanced decay or early decay depending on the amplitude. • Free floating wood >1cm are taken separately from the cavity. • Free floating wood <1cm are not assessed. • Free floating wood does not have structural sound. (IML 2003). 	<p>2-8% (average amplitude 40-50% or 10-30%) - 2-3% (average amplitude 20-10%)</p>
Cavity	<p>Cavity is the absence of wood. Cavities are developed by micro-organisms after injuries or wounds in the trunk, roots of branches. The decomposition of heartwood is formed by dead xylem cells (Zheng et al, 2015).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cavity will be identified as the absence of amplitude. • Free Floating Wood may also be present. 	<p>0% (For all average amplitude)</p>

Appendix e.

Image A shows a complete profile in which overlapping decay/cavity were discounted. The area of cavities remains when it is overlapping with decay. However, advanced decay remains when it overlaps with early decay. When the decay stages are the same the overlapping areas were discounted using AUTOCAD. Image B shows an incomplete profile in which the central area not measured was estimated depending on the drill endings and equally distributed in the area unknown.

Appendix f.

E. regnans images of visual assessment of main cavity and fire scars (Tree ID: DAMAMA05).

Appendix g.

To estimate the biomass of the tree sample for this research project and for the stand of the sites, a factor was calculated to modified the total biomass discounting internal decomposition. The following equations were applied for *E. regnans* ($R^2 = 0.29$) and *N. cunninghamii* ($R^2 = 0.26$) to estimate biomass adjustments.

Appendix h.

Results of the carbon stocks of *E. regnans* compared to Roxburgh et al. (2006) estimated. Total biomass of and *N. cunninghamii* and the total biomass of both species together.

	Euc_reg	Euc_reg	Euc_reg	Not_cun	Not_cun	total	total	total
PLOT_ID	Biomass No Decay	Biomass Roxburgh	Biomass Adjusted	Biomass No Decay	Biomass Adjusted	Biomass No Decay	Biomass Roxburgh	Biomass Adjusted
CV_MA1	1310.898377	551.1241538	1256.144297	24.86528608	25.4444147	1335.763663	551.1241538	1281.588712
CV_RF1	228.4365272	138.3202153	223.6145367	2091.308818	1997.829328	2319.745346	138.3202153	2221.443865
DA_MA1	1911.556568	859.3385239	1828.492454	109.2967942	111.5248125	2020.853362	859.3385239	1940.017267
DA_RF1	514.1575824	239.8729718	500.024567	788.965951	773.6073223	1303.123533	239.8729718	1273.631889
DB_MA1	1108.294563	497.9019742	1074.007265	0	0	1108.294563	497.9019742	1074.007265
DB_RF1	149.5700813	62.16868485	143.7871631	500.5469531	488.3202622	650.1170344	62.16868485	632.1074253
TW_MA1	1082.582762	543.2614527	1058.318364	0	0	1082.582762	543.2614527	1058.318364
TW_RF1	37.84589239	15.47206823	36.5148778	420.2267053	410.772475	458.0725976	15.47206823	447.2873528